

IN-FET
Ionic modulation for Epilepsy Treatment

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1. Executive summary

This report provides a structured overview of the dissemination actions undertaken by the IN-FET project partners during the first two years of activity to ensure an appropriate degree of visibility of the project to all stakeholder categories, from the scientific community to the public. Despite COVID-19-related restrictions, numerous events and actions were undertaken and publications were prepared or submitted, as documented below. A brief outlook on the next year planned or expected actions is given in the last section. A copy of this public document is also available on <https://zenodo.org/communities/in-fet/?page=1&size=20>

2. Dissemination actions

For the first and second year of the IN-FET project, dissemination activities were primarily addressed to the public, rather than to a scientific audience. Given the COVID-19 lockdown and delays in early 2020, dissemination efforts have been focused mostly on the student's community (also as an aid toward the recruiting campaign in support of the project) and to the public (also by means of the website and the social media). Participation to hybrid or remote events allowed the project partners to spread the voice about the project. Engagement at the local or national level was also pursued, mainly via press releases, articles on the press or weekly magazines, etc. . In the third year we could take part to more dissemination activities addressed to the scientific community.

2.1 Dissemination through websites and social media

The **IN-FET website** was launched in February 2020, as the first deliverable of the Management, RRI, Dissemination, Networking, Exploitation Work Package (WP5). Throughout the year, we regularly updated the sections ‘‘Events’’ and ‘‘Press and Dissemination’’ of the website, to announce the events involving the IN-FET project consortium, or to publish press release and divulgation articles that focused on the IN-FET project. Following the feedback from the expert, during our first review meeting, we redesigned the graphical outline of the website (<https://www.in-fet.eu>) and added an introductory video.

We also regularly broadcasted news, press-release, event alters by the IN-FET Twitter (84 followers up to date) and Facebook (45 people liked the page up to date) accounts to advertise our public talks or to engage with the public, discuss neuroprosthetics and give more visibility to our consortium.

We launched a **YouTube channel** (14 people subscribed to it, to date), where we uploaded the videos of our public outreach events: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4299VceGDOSVqmFTgHTIEw> (395 total visualizations up to date).

The description of the IN-FET project has also been published on our **consortium partner MCS' website**: <https://www.multichannelsystems.com/research-projects/fet>, on the website of the Neuronal Dynamics Laboratory at SISSA <https://www.giugliano.info/lab/doku.php> and on the Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn profiles of several consortium members.

2.2 Dissemination through the press

After the kickoff meeting, in February 2020, a **press release**, written with the help of the press office in SISSA, was published on the website of SISSA, on the IN FET website and in the project's social accounts Twitter and Facebook. The press release briefly described the project, making its purpose accessible to all types of audience.

<https://www.in-fet.eu/doku.php/pressrelease1>

<http://phdneurobiology.sissa.it/eng/news/in-fet.aspx>

<https://www.sissa.it/news/eu-funds-%E2%82%AC3m-project-develop-nanodevices-against-epilepsy-and-parkinson%E2%80%99s>

A science **divulgarion article** was published in June 2020 in Panorama, an italian magazine. The title of the article was "Questioni di testa". In the article, Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano explained how stimulating the brain with natural ionic currents (the basic principle behind the IN-FET project) may represent a new treatment for Parkinson.

https://www.in-fet.eu/lib/exe/detail.php/ebwdrvdxkaipxci.jpeg?id=press_dissemination

An **article** about the IN-FET project was published in July 2020 in the monthly magazine of the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia. The title of the article was: "Oltre i confini: quattro progetti tra nanoelettronica, nanotecnologie e neuroscienze" and it described the aim of 4 Horizon 2020 funded projects, in the area of nanotechnologies and neurosciences. https://www.in-fet.eu/doku.php/webmagazine_unimodena

On February 23rd 2021, Prof. Dr. **Michele GIUGLIANO (SISSA)** has been guest of the radio show **RADAR** from the Italian Rai broadcasting, talking about the science dialogue between silicon neurons and biological neurons. The video of the talk has been uploaded on the IN-FET Youtube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tSJpPpzx2dI&t=267s>

On April 15 2021, for the International Day of Researchers, Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano has been briefly interviewed by RAI, the Italian TV broadcasting company. The interview appeared in an article published by ANSA.it:

https://www.ansa.it/friuliveneziagiulia/notizie/2021/04/14/ansaricerca-fvg-studi-poli-eccellenza-ma-pochi-fondi_86ebdd39-91d1-41eb-82f5-9ff8e56a6575.html

In March 2022 Prof. Dr. Renaud Jolivet was interviewed for the Irradium magazine, a publication outlet of the Marie Curie Alumni Association. The focus of the interview were the advantages of European Technological grants, like IN-FET. The interview can be found in the Irradium magazine:

<https://www.mariecuriealumni.eu/mcaa-magazine/march-2022/interviews/advantages-european-technological-grants-mcaa-magazine-march>

On 23 September 2021, the Italian newspaper ‘‘Corriere della Sera’’ published an article with the tile ‘‘Allo studio nanopacemaker contro epilessia e Parkinson’’ explaining the scope of the project IN-FET. <https://www.in-fet.eu/lib/exe/fetch.php/corriere-23-09-21.pdf>

2.3 Dissemination through scientific papers

2.3.1 Manuscripts under revision or preprints

1. *Spike–frequency adaptation is modulated by interacting currents in a Hodgkin-Huxley-type model: Role of the Na,K–ATPase.* **Renaud B. Jolivet**, Pierre J. Magistretti, 2020. Preprint: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.12.148437>; Altmetric score 7 (top 25%).
2. *On the role of theory and modeling in neuroscience.* Daniel Levenstein, Veronica A. Alvarez, Asohan Amarasingham, Habiba Azab, Richard C. Gerkin, Andrea Hasenstaub, Ramakrishnan Iyer, Renaud B. Jolivet, Sarah Marzen, Joseph D. Monaco, Astrid A. Prinz, Salma Quraishi, Fidel Santamaria, Sabyasachi Shivkumar, Matthew F. Singh, David B. Stockton, Roger Traub, Horacio G. Rotstein, Farzan Nadim, A. David Redish: Arxiv, 2020. Preprint: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.13825>; Altmetric score 66 (top 5%).
3. *Modelling of vertical nano-needles as sensing devices for neuronal signal recordings.* Federico Leva, Pierpaolo Palestri, Luca Selmi (2020). TechRxiv. Preprint. <https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.12585086.v1>.
4. *Comparative performance of mutual information and transfer entropy for analyzing the balance of information flow and energy consumption at synapses.* Mireille Conrad and **Renaud B. Jolivet**, 2020. Preprint: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.01.127399>.
5. *Bidirectional modulation of neuronal excitability via ionic actuation of potassium.* Claudio Verardo, Renaud Jolivet, Leandro Julian Mele, Michele Giugliano, Pierpaolo Palestri. To be submitted (2022). Preprint: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.04.03.486896>.
6. *A simulation study of FET-based nanoelectrodes for active intracellular neural recordings.* Leva F., P. Palestri, L. Selmi. IEEE International Conference on Nanotechnology (IEEE-NANO), 2022.
7. *Modeling non-equilibrium ion-transport in ion-selective-membrane/electrolyte interfaces for electrochemical potentiometric sensors,* L. J. Mele, P. Palestri, L. Selmi and M. A. Alam, IEEE Sensors, 2022.
8. *Modeling Selectivity, Sensitivity and Detection Range of Ion-Selective Membranes for Electrochemical Potentiometric Sensors by equilibrium model based on the Poisson-Boltzmann equations,* L. J. Mele, P. Palestri, M. A. Alam and L. Selmi, IEEE Sensors, 2022.

2.3.2 Published

1. *Multidimensional Functional Profiling of Human Neuropathogenic FOXG1 Alleles in Primary Cultures of Murine Pallial Precursors*. Frisari, S.; Santo, M.; Hosseini, A.; Manzati, M.; Giugliano, M.; Mallamaci, A. . Int. J. Mol. Sci. 2022, 23, 1343.
2. *Plasticity and Adaptation in Neuromorphic Biohybrid Systems*. Richard George, Michela Chiappalone, Michele Giugliano, Timothée Levi, Stefano Vassanelli, Johannes Partzsch, Christian Mayr. iScience. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2020.101589>
3. *Modelling Neuromodulated Information Flow and Energetic Consumption at Thalamic Relay Synapses*. Mireille Conrad and Renaud B. Jolivet. Lect. Notes Comput. Sci. 12397: 649-658 (2020). http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61616-8_52.
4. *Modeling Selectivity and Cross-sensitivity in membrane-based potentiometric sensors*, L. J. Mele, P. Palestri and L. Selmi, 2020 Joint International EUROSIOI Workshop and International Conference on Ultimate Integration on Silicon (EUROSIOI-ULIS), 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EUROSIOI-ULIS49407.2020.9365285>.
5. *General model and equivalent circuit for the chemical noise spectrum associated to surface charge fluctuation in potentiometric sensors*, L. J. Mele, P. Palestri and L. Selmi, IEEE Sensors Journal, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2020.3038036>.
6. *Device simulations of ion-sensitive FETs with arbitrary surface chemical reactions*, L. J. Mele, P. Palestri and L. Selmi, 2021 Joint International EUROSIOI Workshop and International Conference on Ultimate Integration on Silicon (EUROSIOI-ULIS), 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EuroSOI-ULIS53016.2021.9560696>
7. *Multiscale simulation analysis of passive and active micro/nanoelectrode for CMOS-based in vitro neural sensing devices*. F. Leva, P. Palestri and L. Selmi. Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A, *in press*. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2021.0013>
8. *Combining an Integrated Sensor Array with Machine Learning for the Simultaneous Quantification of Multiple Cations in Aqueous Mixtures*. Gabrieli, Gianmarco, et al. Analytical Chemistry 93.50 (2021): 16853-16861. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.1c03709>

2.4 Dissemination through other means

1. In February and March 2020, the IN-FET project coordinator, Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano volunteered for two events (one lecture and one debate/interview) organised by SISSA for schools: a series of appointments where students from primary, middle and high school met the scientists working in SISSA and learned about the research they carry out, resulting often in enthusiastic reactions from both sides, the students and the professors. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Mjz4VCeKKsM>
2. In September 2020, in the frame of ESOF 2020 and Science in the City Festival, our IN-FET project coordinator Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano, together with Prof. Dr. Pierpaolo Palestri and

Prof. Dr. Luca Selmi, members of the IN-FET consortium, held a public lecture on “Nanotechnologies and nanoelectronics to cure the brain”. Chairman of the talk was Dr. Valentina Perrera, IN-FET project manager. The public lecture took place inside the seminar room of the Revoltella Museum, downtown in Trieste and was streamed live on YouTube <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sHMQstkcw-o>

About 40 people were in the audience in Museo Revoltella in Trieste (Italy) and other 70 people followed the event live in the Science in the City Festival YouTube channel. The video available on the Science in the City Festival YouTube channel has now reached 556 views (updated to 30th May 2022). The video of the lecture is also permanently visible on the IN-FET YouTube channel, where it reached 89 views (updated to 30th May 2022).

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sHSjptNfq8&t=702s>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sHMQstkcw-o>

<https://events.scienceinthecity2020.eu/en/nanotechnologies-and-nanoelectronics-to-cure-the-brain>

3. Leandro Julian Mele presented “Modeling Selectivity and Cross-sensitivity in membrane-based potentiometric sensors” at 6th Joint International EUROSIOI Workshop and International Conference on Ultimate Integration on Silicon (EUROSIOI-ULIS), 2020 held virtually in Caen, France.
4. We produced and distributed a leaflet to all consortium members and published on our website and social accounts, to synthetically describe the goal of the IN-FET project and the diversity of its consortium composition.
5. Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano, together with Dr. Renaud Jolivet, participated as speakers to the MCAA Virtual Conference on Research and Democracy on the 6 November 2020 15:45 - 16:45 CET, with the talk: At the interface of AI, Neuroscience and Policy.
A summary of the workshop can be found here:
<https://medium.com/marie-curie-alumni/live-from-the-mcaa-virtual-conference-5e5a3114772c>
About 50 viewers listened to the live broadcast. Additionally, the recorded workshop is available on YouTube here <https://youtu.be/GMQQUvaIGJA> and here <https://youtu.be/kvPMzET9cOU>, and had accumulated approximately 188 views by May 2022. The workshop was heavily advertised on Twitter by multiple accounts before and after the event.
6. Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano joined SISSA's “Student Day” on the 5th of March 2021, in a digital format, participating to a round table on Neuroscience and AI <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LjQCrdWmkLk> (85 views on 30th May 2022)
7. Dr. Federico Leva (IUNET-UniMORE, PhD student partly funded by IN-FET) presented his research within the IN-FET project to the international advisory board of the PhD program in Information and Communication Technologies organized by Università di Modena and Reggio Emilia on the 12th March 2021. The attendees were Professors of different disciplines from prestigious European Universities.
8. Prof. Dr. Pierpaolo Palestri (IUNet-Udine) taught a 14h course (March - June 2021) entitled “Interazione tra dispositivi elettronici e neuroni” (Interaction between electronic devices and neurons) for the “Scuola Superiore” of the University of Udine. The course disseminates the results of the activities carried out by partner IUNET in the INFET project
9. We organized a joint FET meeting (online) with the HERMES-FET consortium (www.hermes-fet.eu) that took place on the 30 March 2021. Several speakers from HERMES-FET and IN-FET presented their results to pave the way for future collaboration.

10. Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano presented a talk with the title, "Broad-band brains", for high-school students, within the SISSA for School programme on the 22 and 29 April 2021
11. Gianmarco Gabrieli (IBM Research Europe, PhD student partly funded by IN-FET) presented to the 18th International Meeting on Chemical Sensors (IMCS, Chicago, May 31, 2021) the work on "*Quantification of Multi-Ion Mixtures Using A Machine Learning Assisted Integrated Electronic Tongue Leveraging Mobile and Cloud Platforms*", including the advances on the development of polymeric films within the IN-FET project.
12. Prof. Michele Giugliano gave an invited talk at the Como Lake summer school (Neural circuit complexity: Neuroscience, Models and Robotics (BrainCosmos), <https://brco.lakecomoschool.org> on the 1st of September 2021
13. Dr. Julian Mele, together with Prof. Dr. Pierpaolo Palestri joined the conference "EUROSOLULIS 2021" (Joint International EUROSOL Workshop and International Conference on Ultimate Integration on Silicon) held in Caen (France) on 1-4 Sep 2021 with an oral presentation entitled "*Device simulations of ion-sensitive FETs with arbitrary surface chemical reactions*".
14. Prof. Renaud B. Jolivet participated to a high-level workshop to discuss the future of neurosciences and neurotechnologies "The Neuroscience Summit" on September 6-8, 2021 in Chetzeron, Switzerland.
15. Dr. Diletta Pozzi, Dr. Valentina Perrera and Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano presented the principle behind the IN-FET project, at the booth of SISSA at Trieste Next, a scientific research festival that takes place every year in Trieste, this year on the 24-26 September 2021. Within the same festival, on the 24 September, Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano gave a lecture for high school students with the title: "Il futuro delle neuro-protesi"; and on the 26 September 2021 Dr. Diletta Pozzi and Dr. Michele Giugliano participated to a round table with the title: "AI & Microchips nel cervello: fantascienza o realta'?" <https://www.triestenext.it/tc-events/intelligenza-artificiale-e-microchip-nel-cervello-fantascienza-o-realta>
16. Dr. Jannis Meents was invited as a speaker for the webinar "Vom Labor in die Praxis" ("from lab to application"), organized by the Natural and Medical Sciences Institute of the University Tübingen in November 2021. Jannis presented recent advances at MCS in his talk entitled "Elektronische Systeme für biomedizinische Forschung, Mikroelektrodenarrays und Elektrophysiologie" („Electronic systems for biomedical research, microelectrode arrays and electrophysiology”).
17. In January 2022, Prof. Dr. B. Jolivet was invited to speak at a career panel called "Academia in the US and Beyond at the Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai", organised by the local postdoc association. He discussed extensively the benefits of EU funding, and IN-FET in particular.
18. Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano joined SISSA's "Student Day" on the 25th of February 2022, participating to a lesson on Neuroscience from the title "Neurons and electronic chips: how to spy a neuronal circuit in culture". During the lesson he talked about the IN-FET project and its purpose.
19. On 24 May 2022, Claudio Verardo took part in a workshop organized by the "Scuola Superiore" of the University of Udine (<https://scuolasuperiore.uniud.it/>) for high school students. He presented his work within IN-FET and its connection with the research area of neural interfaces.
20. Claudio Verardo attended the "Neurotechnology" NIN Summer School 2022 (Amsterdam, 2-4 June 2022, <https://summerschool.nin.nl/>), organized by the Netherlands Institute for

Neuroscience. He participated in the poster sessions, presenting his work within IN-FET with the poster “Theoretical and computational study of neuromodulation via ionic actuation of potassium”.

21. Federico Leva attended the “Neurotechnology” NIN Summer School 2022 (Amsterdam, 2-4 June 2022, <https://summerschool.nin.nl/>), organized by the Netherlands Institute for Neuroscience. He participated in the poster sessions, presenting his work within IN-FET with the poster “Numerical simulation analysis of nanoelectrode devices for in-vitro neural sensing”.
22. Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano was invited as a speaker on the 10th June 2022 to the symposium held at the University of Trieste, titled “Scienza in Movimento”, with a talk on artificial intelligence and microchips for the brain, where he talked about the IN-FET project.

2.5 Planned dissemination events

- Talks are on-going with partners of the BEFERROSYNAPTIC (www.beferrosynaptic.eu) H2020 project to organize a joint workshop later in 2022 with invited and contributed talks.
- Prof. Renaud B. Jolivet will write a popular science column for the MCAA magazine Irradium to appear in 2022.
- Claudio Verardo will attend the Federation of European Neuroscience Societies (FENS) Forum Conference (Paris, 9-13 July 2022). Upon acceptance, he will participate in the poster sessions, presenting his work within IN-FET with the poster “Neuromodulation via ionic actuation of potassium: an in silico study”.
- Federico Leva will attend the Federation of European Neuroscience Societies (FENS) Forum Conference (Paris, 9-13 July 2022). Upon acceptance, he will participate in the poster sessions, presenting his work within IN-FET with the poster “Novel field-effect-transistor nanoelectrode probes for active intracellular electrophysiology: a simulation study”.
- Prof. Dr. Renaud will speak at the following workshop in September 2022: ‘Mathematical biology of signaling and metabolism at synapses’, European Conference on Mathematical and Theoretical Biology (ECMTB), Heidelberg, Germany.

3. Summary table

Means of communication	Main target groups	Purpose	Actions done	Date	Other
IN-FET Twitter profile, IN-FET Facebook profile	ALL	To engage with the public, discuss about neuroprosthetics and give more visibility to the IN-FET project	Opening the profiles and posting periodically	February 2020	Twitter 84 followers; Facebook 45 likes, as of today
Project website	ALL	To create a web presence for the project and make the community aware of the IN-FET project’s main aim and consortium composition	The website has been created and advertised on the social channels of IN-FET	February 2020	

YouTube channel	ALL	To upload the videos of our public outreach and scientific dissemination events	Opening the channel, uploading the videos, advertising the channel on the twitter and facebook accounts and on the IN-FET website	February 2020	14 subscribers as of today
Kickoff meeting press release	ALL	To communicate that the IN-FET project was launched and briefly describe its purpose	The press release was published on the website of SISSA, on the IN FET website and in the project's social accounts Twitter and Facebook	February 2020	
SISSA 4 Schools	high school students	To allow students from school to get in touch with scientists and familiarise with their research activities	A series of appointments where students from primary, middle and high school met the scientists working in SISSA and learned about the research they carry out	Periodically every year	
Science divulgation article by Panorama	ALL	To inform the public on the state-of-the-art technologies in neuroscience	Michele Giugliano explained how stimulating the brain with natural ionic currents (the basic principle behind the IN-FET project) may represent a new treatment for Parkinson	June 2020	
Article about the IN-FET project published in the monthly magazine of the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia	ALL, students, professors and staff, mainly from University of Modena and Reggio Emilia	To announce the involvement of UNIMORE in Horizon 2020 funded projects and describe these project's main aim	The article described the scientific focus of 4 different Horizon 2020 funded projects involving nanotechnologies, nano electronics and neuroscience	July 2020	
Public talk "Nanotechnologies and nanoelectronics to cure the brain"	ALL	To take part in the ESOF2020 conference with a public outreach event centered on IN-FET project	The public lecture took place inside the seminar room of the Revoltella Museum, downtown in Trieste and was streamed live on YouTube	September 2020	
Conference presentation	scientists	To present results on modeling advances	Leandro Julian Mele presented "Modeling Selectivity and Cross-sensitivity in membrane-based potentiometric sensors" at 6 th Joint International EUROSIOI Workshop and International Conference on Ultimate Integration on Silicon (EUROSIOI-ULIS), 2020 held virtually in Caen, France.	September 1-30, 2020	
Leaflet	ALL	To have a brochure for a quick presentation of IN-FET project's main aim and consortium composition	The leaflet highlights the most important aspects of the IN-FET project and summarises its goal. It has been distributed to all consortium members	November 2020	
Online workshop	Neuroscientists/scientists	MCAA virtual conference on Research and democracy. A talk to discuss the interface between Neuroscience, AI and policy	A presentation by Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano and Prof. Dr. Renaud Jolivet	November 2020	Reached 188 viewers total as of today
Public interview	ALL	To make divulgation on Italian top level scientific research in neurobiology	On Prof. Dr. Michele GIUGLIANO (SISSA) has been guest of the radio show RADAR from the Italian Rai broadcasting, talking about the science dialogue between silicon neurons and biological neurons. The video of the talk has been uploaded on the IN-FET Youtube channel: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tSjNpPzx2dI&t=267s	23 February 2021	
Article on Irradium Magazine	Scientists	To discuss EU funding opportunities	In March 2022 Prof. Dr. Renaud Jolivet was interviewed for the Irradium magazine, a publication outlet of the Marie Curie Alumni Association. The focus of the interview were the advantages of European Technological	March 2021	

			grants, like IN-FET. The interview can be found in the Irradium magazine: https://www.mariecuriealumni.eu/mcaa-magazine/march-2022/interviews/advantages-european-technological-grants-mcaa-magazine-march		
SISSA 4 Schools	High school students	To make divulgation on the future of neurosciences and neurotechnologies	Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano joined SISSA's "Student Day" on the 5th of March 2021, in a digital format, participating to a round table on Neuroscience and AI https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LjOCrdWmkLk (85 views on 30th May 2022)	5 March 2021	
Institute presentation	Scientists	To present latest results	Dr. Federico Leva (IUNET-UniMORE, PhD student partly funded by IN-FET) presented his research within the IN-FET project to the international advisory board of the PhD program in Information and Communication Technologies organized by Università di Modena and Reggio Emilia on the 12 th March 2021. The attendees were Professors of different disciplines from prestigious European Universities.	12 March 2021	
Online workshop	Neuroscientists/scientists	To pave the way for future collaborations a Joint lab meeting between the HERMES-FET and IN-FET project has been held online	Talks by scientists in both consortia	30 March 2021	Online workshop
Course	University students	To inform students about research activities on the edge between electronics and neuroscience	14h course held by Prof. Dr. Pierpaolo Palestri (in Italian) entitled "Interazione tra dispositivi elettronici e neuroni" (Interaction between electronic devices and neurons) for the "Scuola Superiore" of the University of Udine	March-June 2021	7 students
Public interview	ALL	To make divulgation on Italian top level scientific research in neurobiology	In occasion of the International Day of Researchers, Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano has been briefly interviewed by the RAI, the Italian TV broadcasting company. The interview resulted in an article published in ANSA.it: https://www.ansa.it/friuliveneziaigiulia/notizie/2021/04/14/ansaricerca-fvg-studi-poli-eccellenza-ma-pochi-fondi_86ebdd39-91d1-41eb-82f5-9ff8e56a6575.html	15 April 2021	
SISSA 4 Schools	ALL	To allow students from school to get in touch with scientists and familiarise with their research activities	Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano presented a talk with the title, "Broad-band brains", for high-school students, within the SISSA for School programme on the 22 and 29 April 2021	22, 29 April 2021	
Conference presentation	scientists	To present results on development of polymeric films on miniaturized electrodes	Gianmarco Gabrieli presented "Quantification of Multi-Ion Mixtures Using A Machine Learning Assisted Integrated Electronic Tongue Leveraging Mobile and Cloud Platforms" at 18th IMCS conference 2021 held in Chicago, USA	May 31 2021	
Conference presentation	scientists	To present results on modeling advances	Leandro Julian Mele presented "Device simulations of ion-sensitive FETs with arbitrary surface chemical reactions" at 7th Joint International EUROSIOI Workshop and International Conference on Ultimate Integration on Silicon (EUROSIOI-ULIS), 2021 held in Caen, France.	August 31-September 4, 2021	Approx. 70 participants
Conference presentation	scientists	To present results obtained in the Neuronal Dynamics Laboratory in SISSA	Prof. Michele Giugliano has been invited to give a talk with the title "Correlation Transfer in Cortical Neurons" at the Como Lake summer school (Neural circuit complexity: Neuroscience, Models and Robotics	September 1, 2021	

			(BrainCosmos), https://brco.lakecomosc.hool.org		
Online workshop	Scientists	To discuss the future of neurosciences and neurotechnologies	Renaud B. Jolivet participated with a talk to “The Neuroscience Summit” in Chetzeron, Switzerland	September 6-8, 2021	
Science fair Trieste NEXT	ALL	To make divulgation on the future of neurosciences and neurotechnologies	Dr. Diletta Pozzi, Dr. Valentina Perrera and Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano presented the principle behind the IN-FET project, at the booth of SISSA at Trieste Next, a scientific research festival that takes place every year in Trieste, this year on the 24-26 September 2021.	24 – 26 September 2021	
Science fair Trieste NEXT	ALL	To take part in the Trieste next scientific festival with a public outreach event centered on IN-FET project	Lecture for high school students with the title: “Il futuro delle neuro-protesi; round table with the title: “AI & Microchips nel cervello: fantascienza o realta?”; presence of the IN-FET project representatives at the SISSA booth.	26 September 2021	
Webinar	Scientists	To present latest results on technology development	Dr. Jannis Meents was invited as a speaker for the webinar “Vom Labor in die Praxis” (“from lab to application”), organized by the Natural and Medical Sciences Institute of the University Tübingen in November 2021. Jannis presented recent advances at MCS in his talk entitled “Elektronische Systeme für biomedizinische Forschung, Mikroelektrodenarrays und Elektrophysiologie“ („Electronic systems for biomedical research, microelectrode arrays and electrophysiology”).	November 2021	
Talk	Scientists	To discuss about EU funding opportunities	In January 2022, Prof. Dr. B. Jolivet was invited to speak at a career panel called “Academia in the US and Beyond at the Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai”, organized by the local postdoc association. He discussed extensively the benefits of EU funding, and IN-FET in particular.	January 2022	
SISSA4 Schools Student day	ALL, high school students	To make divulgation on the future of neurosciences and neurotechnologies	Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano joined SISSA's “Student Day” on the 25th of February 2022, participating to a lesson on Neuroscience from the title “Neurons and electronic chips: how to spy a neuronal circuit in culture”. During the lesson he talked about the IN-FET project and its purpose.	25 February 2022	
Workshop	Scientists	To present latest results	On 24 May 2022, Claudio Verardo took part in a workshop organized by the “Scuola Superiore” of the University of Udine (https://scuolasuperiore.uniud.it/) for high school students. He presented his work within IN-FET and its connection with the research area of neural interfaces.	24 May 2022	
Summer school	Scientists	To present latest results	Claudio Verardo attended the “Neurotechnology” NIN Summer School 2022 (Amsterdam, 2-4 June 2022, https://summerschool.nin.nl/), organized by the Netherlands Institute for Neuroscience. He participated in the poster sessions, presenting his work within IN-FET with the poster “Theoretical and computational study of neuromodulation via ionic actuation of potassium”.	2-4 June 2022	

Summer school	Scientists	To present latest results	Federico Leva attended the “Neurotechnology” NIN Summer School 2022 (Amsterdam, 2-4 June 2022, https://summerschool.nin.nl/), organized by the Netherlands Institute for Neuroscience. He participated in the poster sessions, presenting his work within IN-FET with the poster “Numerical simulation analysis of nanoelectrode devices for in-vitro neural sensing”.	2-4 June 2022	
Talk	University students	To make divulgation on the future of neurosciences and neurotechnologies	Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano was invited as a speaker on the 10th June 2022 to the symposium held at the University of Trieste, titled “Scienza in Movimento”, with a talk on artificial intelligence and microchips for the brain, where he talked about the IN-FET project.	10 June 2022	
Scientific publications or preprints in peer reviewed journals	Neuroscientists/scientists	Scientific dissemination of novel findings and results obtained within the IN-FET project	<p>Under revision or preprints</p> <p><i>Spike-frequency adaptation is modulated by interacting currents in an Hodgkin-Huxley-type model: Role of the Na,K-ATPase.</i> Renaud B. Jolivet, Pierre J. Magistretti, 2020. Preprint: https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.12.148437; Altmetric score 7 (top 25%).</p> <p><i>On the role of theory and modeling in neuroscience.</i> Daniel Levenstein, Veronica A. Alvarez, Asohan Amarasingham, Habiba Azab, Richard C. Gerkin, Andrea Hasenstaub, Ramakrishnan Iyer, Renaud B. Jolivet, Sarah Marzen, Joseph D. Monaco, Astrid A. Prinz, Salma Quraishi, Fidel Santamaria, Sabyasachi Shivkumar, Matthew F. Singh, David B. Stockton, Roger Traub, Horacio G. Rotstein, Farzan Nadim, A. David Redish: Arxiv, 2020. Preprint: http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.13825; Altmetric score 66 (top 5%).</p> <p><i>Modelling of vertical nano-needles as sensing devices for neuronal signal recordings.</i> Federico Leva, Pierpaolo Palestri, Luca Selmi (2020). TechRxiv. Preprint. https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.12585086.v1.</p> <p><i>Comparative performance of mutual information and transfer entropy for analyzing the balance of information flow and energy consumption at synapses.</i> Mireille Conrad and Renaud B. Jolivet, 2020. Preprint: https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.01.127392.</p> <p><i>A simulation study of FET-based nanoelectrodes for active intracellular neural recordings.</i> Leva F., P. Palestri, L. Selmi. IEEE International Conference on Nanotechnology (IEEE-NANO), 2022.</p> <p><i>Modeling non-equilibrium ion-transport in ion-selective-membrane/electrolyte interfaces for electrochemical potentiometric sensors,</i> L. J. Mele, P. Palestri, L. Selmi and M. A. Alam, IEEE Sensors, 2022.</p> <p><i>Modeling Selectivity, Sensitivity and Detection Range of Ion-Selective Membranes for Electrochemical Potentiometric Sensors by equilibrium</i></p>		Neuroscientists/scientists

			<p><i>model based on the Poisson-Boltzmann equations</i>, L. J. Mele, P. Palestri, M. A. Alam and L. Selmi, IEEE Sensors, 2022.</p> <p><i>Bidirectional modulation of neuronal excitability via ionic actuation of potassium</i>. Claudio Verardo, Renaud Jolivet, Leandro Julian Mele, Michele Giugliano, Pierpaolo Palestri. To be submitted (2022). Preprint: https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.04.03.486896</p> <p>.</p> <p>Published</p> <p><i>Plasticity and Adaptation in Neuromorphic Biohybrid Systems</i>. Richard George, Michela Chiappalone, Michele Giugliano, Timothée Levi, Stefano Vassanelli, Johannes Partzsch, Christian Mayr. iScience. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2020.101589</p> <p><i>Modelling Neuromodulated Information Flow and Energetic Consumption at Thalamic Relay Synapses</i>. Mireille Conrad and Renaud B. Jolivet. Lect. Notes Comput. Sci. 12397: 649-658 (2020). http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61616-8_52.</p> <p><i>Modeling Selectivity and Cross-sensitivity in membrane-based potentiometric sensors</i>, L. J. Mele, P. Palestri and L. Selmi, 2020 Joint International EUROSIOI Workshop and International Conference on Ultimate Integration on Silicon (EUROSIOI-ULIS), 2020. https://doi.org/10.1109/EUROSIOI-ULIS49407.2020.9365285.</p> <p><i>General model and equivalent circuit for the chemical noise spectrum associated to surface charge fluctuation in potentiometric sensors</i>, L. J. Mele, P. Palestri and L. Selmi. IEEE Sensors Journal, 2021. https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2020.3038036.</p> <p><i>Device simulations of ion-sensitive FETs with arbitrary surface chemical reactions</i>, L. J. Mele, P. Palestri and L. Selmi, 2021 Joint International EUROSIOI Workshop and International Conference on Ultimate Integration on Silicon (EUROSIOI-ULIS), 2021. https://doi.org/10.1109/EuroSIOI-ULIS53016.2021.9560696</p> <p><i>Multiscale simulation analysis of passive and active micro/nanoelectrode for CMOS-based in vitro neural sensing devices</i>. F. Leva, P. Palestri and L. Selmi. Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A, in press. https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2021.0013</p> <p><i>Combining an Integrated Sensor Array with Machine Learning for the Simultaneous Quantification of Multiple Cations in Aqueous Mixtures</i>. Gabrieli, Gianmarco, et al. Analytical Chemistry 93.50 (2021): 16853-16861.</p>	
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Table1. Summary of the dissemination activities per target community and action.

4. Conclusions and outlook

The first two years and a half of the project led to a more than adequate total number of dissemination actions, both toward the public and the scientific community. Links to other projects in the same or similar research areas have been established which are expected to enhance the effectiveness of the outcomes and expand the perimeter of stakeholders reached. As project activities are beginning to produce results of scientific relevance, IN-FET partners will steer their main dissemination actions toward scientific papers on peer reviewed journals and conferences.